

PEOPLE RAISED IN TURKESTAN TERRITORY IN 1916 INVESTIGATION PROCESSES OF THE UPRISING

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Annotation: In this case, on the basis of the mobilization of the Rossiya emperor to the labor force of 1916, a brief description of the investigation process carried out on persons who took an active part in the iaql uprising, which was raised after the new decree, and who called for the uprising.

Keywords: A.N. Kuropatkin, M.R. Yerafeev, Akbar Omarbayev, Abdujalil Kadirav, Astangul Yusufbayev, Abdullakan Khalmatov, I.A.Brzhezitsky, A.N.Sologub, Ivan Govorov, Semey Rusanov, Grigory Pogorelov, Ilya Tarasov, Dmitry Borodin.

Information and various opinions were also expressed about the uprisings in the saxifics of the Russian press. Genarel-governor of Turkestan A.N. It was never possible that Kuropatkin would not take them for granted. He carried out tough measures aimed at suppressing uprisings and punishing his participants.

First of all, in 1916, a martial law was introduced throughout the territory of Turkestan. Also, military field courts were formed and insurgents were heavily investigated. In this regard, the Russian military Minister D.S. Shuvayev temporary executor of the post of Governor-General of Turkestan M.R. In a telegram sent to yerofeev on July 17, 1916, it is said: "in order to quickly see the work of the participants in the uprising, urgently draw up a military field court. Let these members of the court be organized only from the officers in the movement and sent to all the places of the territory where they are found."

The Tsarist administration, based on the rules of martial law, further sharpened the repressions. On July 9, 1916, the following persons in Andijan were investigated and brought to court: Abdusattorhakim Akshov, Abdujabborgori Roziboyev, Mamadali Abdukarimov, Abdullajon Hayitmetov, Joraqori Zunnunboyev, Akbar Umarbayev, Mullaabdulhaq Khalfayev, Ashurali Ismailov, Mamajonmulla Atakhanov, Mullakarimmirza Azizkhojayev, Abdujalil Kadyrov, among them are Nasir Abdurakhmanov, mullamaqsudali ustanishonbayev, yusufjan Tashpalatov, Lambibay Saliaminov, Astangul Yusufbayev, Osmanjan Maraimov, Akhtam Yangildin, Mamasadik Rozibayev and Yusufkhaja Mukhammadsharifkhujayev .

In the indictment of the assistant military prosecutor Simonov, the above-mentioned people were condemned in Andijan for armed with hoe, sticks, bricks and other things, making noise and attacking the tsarist administration.

Specifically the beating of Abdusattor mirshab and the sword of military Tarasov accused of spinning in the head. Abdujabborkori Ruziboyev, on the other hand, encouraged haloyuk to beat the representatives of the administration. Abdullajan Kholmatov, Yusufjon Tashpulatov, Mullaabdulhaq Ashurkhalfayev were accused of attacking the head of the village . Other insurgents were also charged with similar charges.

The indictment indicated that an angry crowd stoned him when someone called Kasimjon Madkosimov campaigned to spread to the rebels and go to Labor. Kasimjon Madkosimov, seriously wounded in the head, died.

As a witness, representatives of the administration were mainly involved in the court. In them, the head of the Andijan uyezd was Colonel I.A.Brzhhezitsky, from the mirshabs A.N.Sologub, Ivan Govorov, Semey Rusanov, Grigory Pogorelov, Ilya Tarasov, Dmitry Borodin, Vasily Sipliyakov, Stepan Shirinkin and others are 26 people in total. Among the representatives of the local nation, one of the neighborhood agakols of the city, Abdukadir Abdugafforov, Yusufjon Chorishev and the city Deputy Mirali Umarboyev, passed the testimony.

So all the witnesses were chosen from the official ones. It was a work done with a certain purpose. The indictment of the prosecutor under comment is made by the Governor General of Turkestan A.N.It was carried out with the approval of Kuropatkin. Investigative work was also carried out over the participants of the rising lambgolon in the village of Dalvarzin in uyezd. At the time of this uprising, the head of the volost Khakimbek Roziboyev and his mirshabs Temir Nabatqulov and Karimjon Abdulvakhobov were killed. Marasul Madyarov, Ismailhaji Shakirkhajiye, Tajibay Khalfayev, Said Shakiraliyev, Khasanbaymulla Kuchov, Teshabek Khamdamkhajiye, Khazratkul Khamdamkhajiye, Muhammadazim Mullaumrzagov, Makhmudali Khidirbayev, Atajan Ortiqbayev, Abdurakhmankhaji Gazigulov, Abdugarimkhaja Khusainkhajiye, in relation to mullaabdurakhman Mullaabduattorov, Abdullakhoja Abdukodirhojiye, Jalil Ulugaliyev, Abdulvokhid Khasanhojiye, Muhammadjan Muhammadboboboev, Usman Alikodirkulov and others, criminal cases were initiated and their cases were brought to court.

Four women, consisting of the murdered volost steward Khakimbek Mullaro'zibekov, Mehrinisa Makhmudalibayeva, Khosiyat Abdugafurova, Gümüşbibi Yulduzboyeva and Tajibibibi Rizojojieva, filed an application with the Turkistan military court in order to recover the loophat brought by the rebels. The application indicated that six young children were orphaned from markhum, and it was announced that he received a salary of 500 soums in 1 year . He earned 6,000 soums from cotton and farming products in general. In addition, a person who was taken to manage the farm after his death was charged 100 soums per month and 1,200 soums per year. Thus, the tragedy of the volost steward was a rather big disaster and fell into a difficult situation. They demanded that the rebels levy the calamity. It was appealed to the court to meet the demand.

According to the prosecutor's indictment, Mullaobid Mullahojiyev, Jumaqozi Usmonpolvonov, Parniboy Abduvaliyev and Isibboy Nazarov in the village of Chuama of Moyghir volosti showed enthusiasm in the uprising. In particular, Mullaubid Mullaabdoshkhojiev, calling on the people to rise, took an important place in the rise of the uprising. Together with him, Jumaqozi Usmonpolvonov and Isibboy Nazarov took an active part in the attack on the volost chief and his father's household.

"The rebels," the indictment says, " went against the decree of the emperor's Supreme khazrats on obtaining labor, armed with sticks, stones and axes, and gathered in the market. They shouted," We will kill the volost chief and other list — makers." The crowd stormed the apartment of the village elder Kirghizboy Karimbayev and his father Karimboy Turakulov, breaking and breaking gates, windows and doors, plundered his property. For their participation in this uprising, Abdulla Kasimov, Mulla Ismailov, Mamatkul Abdulkasimov,

Omonboy Rizakulbayev, Akbarali Ahmadaliyev, Tuychibay Turakulbayev, Makhmudali Tokhtasinbayev, Mirzayokub Suleymanov, Dildor Temirbayev, Kyrgyzboy Rizakulov, Mamatyakub Egamberdikhojiyev, Abdunigman Kasimbayev, Mullaraimberdi ustaegamberdiyev, Mirakhmad Poryabayev, Yulduz Maqsudov, Tashboy Aliqulov and Khaydarmirza Rahmonov were investigated and brought to court .

Together, the indicated persons were accused of participating in the murder of the village fiftieth leader Kipchokboy Mirzayev.

The prosecutor's indictment was approved by the Governor-General of Turkestan Kuropatkin, and the case of the "criminals" was sent to court. Of the active participants in the uprising, who were in the village of Sufi of jalakuduk volosti, 48 people were investigated and brought to court. Of these, the Yangibay Mamarasulov, the Ramqorboy, the Marayim Qasobov, the Paykarim Sufievs went to the front lines of the uprising. Mullayoldosh Mirzasulaymonov, the steward of the jalakuduk volost, and the village elder Comrade Hayitboyevs, who showed enthusiasm in the murder. Also, people such as Safar Kosimkhojayev, Abdulkosim Sadiqkhojayev and Nasirkhoja were killed by the rebels with a stone's throw for standing on the side of the volost elder.

Eyewitnesses indicate that the head of volost, Yangiboy Mamarasulov, was led to kill the village elder by the Ramqorboy, Marayim Qasobovs. They were killed by those who were shown when the old man became dead after the beatings. A group of insurgents in the village of Qalandar-Qahguncha on the prosecutor's indictment was recommended to the court. It shows that the crowd condemned the people of the team by bringing it to the middle of the Pentecost Esonkul Raimkulov in order to make a list of labourers without permission and demanded to give the list. Having received his refusal, lomon killed him. In this case, 7 people: Abdurakhman Mirzakhusainov, Juraboy UstaToshev, Kamal Madaminov, Maulim Egamberdiev, Iskhak O'rozboev, Orzikul Madisaboy and Turaboy Dostmatovs were submitted to the court. The captains of agitlon in the nearby village of Norin volost, such as Khusht Musaboyev, Osmangul Mavlonhojiyev, Osmanamin Almanboyev and Mullakhonboya Abdudukodirov, were presented to the court.

References:

1. Suyunova A. The national liberation struggle of 1916 in Turkestan (on the example of Syrdarya region). - T.: 1997. - 131 pages
2. Kovalev AP The rear workers of Turkestan during the First World War. Tashkent. 1957 The same: the revolutionary situation of 1915-1917 and its manifestation in Turkestan. Tashkent. 1971
3. Ismailova J. National liberation struggles in the Fergana Valley. - T.: Ghafur Ghulam Publishing House. 2003 - 320 pages
4. Akhmadzhanov G.A. Russian Empire in Central Asia (history and historiography of the colonial policy of tsarism in Turkestan). T. 1995
5. Tursunov H. The popular uprising of 1916 in Uzbekistan. - T.: Uzbekistan, 1966. - 170 pages
6. Kastelskaya Z.D. The main prerequisites for the 1916 uprising in Uzbekistan M., 1972

7. Sodikov H. Turkestan's colonial policy and the struggle for independence (20th century) - Tashkent.1994
8. Choriyev Z. Turkestan laborers: consequences mobilization mobilization and his (1916-1917) .- T. Fan, 1999. – 334 – pages
- 9.Usenboev K. Uprising of 1916 in Kirgion Frunze, 1967

